

DEVELOPMENT OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS IN CHINA

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About two thousand years ago, a typical composite was found in China, that is, Chinese people have used nature hemp fibers reinforce tung tree oil lacquer to make art hand crafts, even this technique was kept till now. Besides, technical book in which describing the skill in detail was also found over five hundred years ago. However, the real manufacturing of composites in industrial scale were begun in 1958. This new material was paid much attention to and supported by Chinese Government, so that, the development period of composite materials was started in this country.

MANUFACTURE AND APPLICATION

A. Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastics (GFRP)

* Raw Materials: Rowing, woven rowings, woven cloth or tape, chopped strand mat of E glass, medium alkali glass, refrasil and small quantity of S-glass are commercially produced.

Resin for GFRP are mainly unsaturated polyesters include for general purpose, flame retardent, water resistance, chemical resistance and other special requirements. Certain amount of epoxy, phenolic and furan resins are also supplied.

*Processing

The commercial production processes relate to hand layer up, spray up, filament winding, pultrusion, continuous corrugated sheeting, SMC moulding, prepreg (for pipe and panel). Recently some state-of-the-art process such as RTM and soft mold moulding (silicon rubber mold) are also considered.

*Application

GFRP products have been successfully availed in the following fields. They are

1. Building materials: Cooling tower, bath unit, corrugated sheet, mobile house, fan blade, window frame and door, large carving, waterspout, cold-storage, grating.
2. Communication: All size antenna and radome.
3. Marine: Pleasure boat, fishing boat, working boat, life boat, hovercraft.
4. Chemical engineering: Pipe and fittings, pipe for filtration, various tanks, vessels, valves, chimney and anticorrosive lining.
5. Transportation: Over head crossing bridge, bridge sign post, car body, structural components for train.
6. Energy: Wind mill blade, axial fan blade, cover for solar energy installations, retaining ring for generator, bracing ring for turbo-genera-

tor, high tension insulator, housing for capacitors.

7. Others: Acoustic equipment, copper plated laminate sheet for electronic purpose, medical care, sporting goods, safety helmet, artificial arm and leg, supporting column for mine.

The total yield in 1986 is approximately 67,000 tons, and the annual average increasing rate from 1980 to 1986 is 29%.

In short, although the applications of GFRP cover a wide range in China, but the quantity is not enough.

Since it faces a lot of problems, for instance, the production is relatively small, less varieties and high cost. Therefore, a serious competition with other traditional materials has befallen on the GFRP in China.

B. Advanced Composite Materials (ACM)

* Raw materials: Recently high performance reinforcement to be used in ACM here is only PAN based carbon fiber. The total yield per year is more than 100 tons, and its typical properties are similar as T300 from Toray Co. produced in the early of 1980's. The resin to be provided for ACM are mainly epoxy series.

* Processing: Processing of ACM involves vacuum bag and autoclave method, filament winding, injection moulding from short carbon fiber/thermoplastic pellets.

* Application

1. Aeronautics and Astronautics: vertical tail structure, airduct lining and secondary loading structures for jet airplane, antenna, skin of apogee rocket for various satellites, fairing and light weight shell structure of the launch vehicles.

2. Loom: shuttle and gear.

3. Sporting goods: fishing rod, tennis or shuttlecock racket, race bicycle, canoe, and swimming web.

4. Others: X-ray table bed, machine components.

Production of ACM in China still place on small scale, since it has problems on high cost and uncertain reliability.

RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

* Reinforcements and resins: High performance reinforcements are researched in several laboratories, they are polyamide fibers, pitch base graphite fibers, SiC fiber from CVD process and polycarbosilane precursors (include Si-Ti-C fiber), SiC whiskers.

A lot of state-of-the-art resins both thermoplastic and thermoset are also studied in laboratories, such as PES, PPS, PEK, PEEK, PMI and PI.

* Processing of new composites and its applications

Some of institutions take account of research and development on new composites relate to metal matrix composites, carbon/carbon composite, ceramic matrix composites and cement matrix composite.

1. Metal matrix composites (MMC) includes carbon or graphite and SiC continuous fibers reinforced Al or Mg, ceramic whiskers and particles reinforced Al, alumina silicate short fiber reinforced Al, carbon (graphite) fiber reinforced Cu and Pb etc.

The processing of the MMC are touch upon vacuum hot press from C/Al

composite wire (in which carbon fiber infiltrated with molten aluminum after surface treated by CVD or other process), squeeze casting, vacuum and pressure infiltration.

The tensile strength of unidirectional G/Al is over 750 MPa and SiC/Al is about 500 MPa.

C/Al and C/Mg are attempted to apply to antenna, lens tube and support strut of satellites. SiCp/Al is considered to produce piston and connecting rod of Diesel engine.

2. Carbon/carbon composite is produced by CVD or carbonization from 3D carbon fiber woven preform infiltrated with pitch resin.

C/C composite products are attempt to produce nozzle or other ablative parts of rocket and brake block for airplane landing wheels.

3. Ceramic and cement matrix composite are also considered in certain laboratories.

* Interfaces in polymer and metal matrix composites.

1. Surface treatment of fibers:

Various silane coupling agent are investigated to improve GFRP mechanical properties. Various surface treatment method for carbon fiber are also studied, involves oxidized by air or O₃ and electrolytic oxidation, electrodeposition of polyelectrolytics and electropolymerization of electrolytic monomers.

2. Interfacial reaction in metal or ceramic matrix composites:

Investigation interfacial reaction in MMC or CeMC relate to characterization of interfacial reactions, and interfacial reaction influence on the properties of composites.

3. Theoretical understanding of composite interface:

Thermodynamics and kinetics of wetting and bonding behaviour on interface, interface modeling, new determination or characterization techniques are taken up.

* Mechanics on composite materials.

There is a large research team deals with mechanics on composite in China. Their researching works almost cover all the field of mechanics on composite. It involves mechanical properties and its characterization. collision, impact or other properties on transient load, strength, failure, fracture, fatigue, creep and viscoelastic properties, plasticity, mechanical testing methods, properties of stress wave, hygrothermal effect on mechanical properties, structure analysis and design, interlaminar stress, residue stress during curing process, interfacial mechanics, non destructive evaluation, connecting and joint etc.

Recently, Chinese scientist of mechanics begin to transfer their interest from the structural mechanics to deal with material science and to solve practical problems on composite mechanics both in processing or application durations, even predict the lifetime or reliability of the composites.

ACADEMIC ACTIVITIES AND EDUCATION

* Academic organizations for composite materials:

The main academic organizations on composite in China are as follows.

1. FRP (FRP/composite) committee of Chinese silicate society (CSS) was found in 1973.
2. Council of Composite Materials of China Society of Aeronautics and Astronautics (CSAA) was found in 1982.
3. The China FRP Industrial Association was found in 1984.
4. China Society of Composite Materials was found in the early of 1989.

There are also some speciality groups on composite belong to other societies, such as Chinese Society on Mechanics(CSM) and Chinese Society of Aerospace (CSA) etc.

*Conference on composite

An national biannual conference on composite materials hosted by CSAA, CSM and CSA association committee was begun at 1980, and another national biannual conference on FRP (FRP/composite) organized by CSS was started at 1973.

* Journals

The two main journals for composite materials are Acta Materiae Compositae Sinica and Journal of FRP and Composite. Some related papers may be published in certain journals such as Journal of Engineering Plastics and Application, Material Science Progress and Material Technology on Aerospace Application etc.

*Institution, centre and researching group on composite

More than 40 Institutes, Centres and researching groups are distributed all over the country. They belong to universities, Chinese Academy of Science, Ministry of Aeronautics and Astronautics and Bureau of Architectural Materials etc. Total number of senior scientist is over 500 persons.

* Education

There are at least seven universities and institutes have courses on composite materials both for undergraduate and graduate students, and have educated a large number of engineers and scientists in analysis, design, fabrication, testing and evaluation, research and development of composite materials and structures. Some of the universities and institutes can confer M.S and Ph.D degree on graduate studies after they have gone through qualification and thesis argumentation.

Although composite material has been listed in the material development plan of hightech in China, but it exists large distance far from developed countries. We think it would be shortening in the future, but we still have a long way to go.